

ISic1180

Funerary inscription for (?)Marcus Flavius Tuendus

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2019-07-09 - Jonathan Prag revised file based on work for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Dug up in 1771 in the ruins of ancient Halaesa; recorded in 1784 as preserved at Montereale (= Monreale?), 'in monasterio Canonicorum regularium Benedictinae familiae'; now lost?

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, lost

Physical Description

No description of the stone is preserved

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

The text is recorded in the antiquarian tradition over 6 lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No description exists, but Castelli 1784 transcribes with lunate sigma and mostly lunate epsilon

Letter heights:

Line 1-6: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: unknown mm

Text

1. Φιλίππου
2. Φίλιππος
3. Σεκόνδος
4. Μᾶρ(κος) Φλουάβ
5. ιος Τουένδος
6. χᾶϊρε

Apparatus

Text of Castelli 1784

Translation (en)

Philippus Secundus, son of Philippus; Marcus Flavius Tuendus, greetings

Commentary

Castelli observed that the first three lines were unusual, seemingly recording the patronymic first. Franz in CIG proposed correcting the end of lines 1 and 2 so that the order was reversed. Kaibel in IG instead despaired of making sense of what he assumed to be either errors of Castelli or the result of a forgery. It is unclear whether this is in fact one individual with multiple names with the patronymic unusually placed first, or two separate individuals. Without the possibility of checking the stone, no certainty is possible. Tuendus is not a common name but is attested in Italy in the imperial period, and the text must be imperial in date (second to fourth century?). Facella (2006: 290 n.41) notes the various attestations of Secundus as a name in the imperial period in Sicily.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492785

PHI 140663

Bibliography

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